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Sub-Sahara African Journal of Psychology and Contemporary Issues (SAJPCI)

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The Editor-in-Chief

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**From Offline Isolation to Online Escape: Psychosocial Pathways to Digital Refuge-
Seeking Behaviours among Adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria**

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Abstract

Adolescents increasingly turn to digital platforms as sources of emotional and psychological comfort, particularly in contexts of social isolation and intensive social media engagement. Despite growing concern, little is known about the psychosocial predictors of digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria. This study examined the influence of loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction on digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan. A cross-sectional research design was adopted, using a purposive sampling technique to recruit 415 in-school adolescents (males = 46.4%, females = 53.6%) with the mean age of 14.89 years (SD = 1.46). Data were collected using the Digital Refuge Scale, Loneliness Scale, Emotional Dependency Scale, and Social Media Addiction Scale. Hierarchical multiple regression analysis showed that loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction jointly predicted digital refuge ($R = .45$; $R^2 = .20$; $F(3, 269) = 22.21$, $p < .001$). Loneliness ($\beta = .320$, $t = 5.38$, $p < .001$) and social media addiction ($\beta = .152$, $t = 2.57$, $p < .05$) were significant independent predictors, whereas emotional dependency was not ($\beta = .107$, $t = 1.71$, $p > .05$). Independent samples t-test revealed no significant gender difference in digital refuge ($t(381) = 0.07$, $p > .05$). One-way ANOVA indicated that parental occupation ($F(3, 364) = 1.898$, $p > .05$) and parental marital status ($F(4, 369) = 0.905$, $p > .05$) did not significantly influence digital refuge. In conclusion, the study demonstrates that loneliness and social media addiction are key psychological predictors of digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan. These findings highlight the need for school- and community-based interventions that address adolescent loneliness and promote healthy social media use to support psychological well-being.

Keywords: Adolescents, Digital Refuge, Emotional Dependency, Loneliness, Social Media Addiction

Introduction

Adolescence is a critical developmental stage marked by identity exploration, heightened emotional sensitivity, and increasing reliance on peer and social networks for validation (Aruoture & Adegoke, 2024; Onuoha et al., 2024). In Nigeria, the rapid proliferation of smartphones and digital platforms has transformed adolescents' social and emotional landscapes, creating both opportunities and challenges for psychosocial development. Social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Instagram, TikTok, and Snapchat have evolved from tools for communication and entertainment into psychologically immersive environments, offering adolescents spaces to seek solace, affirmation, and emotional regulation (Ajayi et al., 2024; Badejo & Oriade, 2024; Balogun & Aruoture). This behaviour, commonly referred to as digital refuge, is characterised not by the frequency of online engagement but by the underlying psychological motivation to escape offline stressors, manage emotional discomfort, or compensate for unmet social needs (Melodia et al., 2022; Chen et al., 2025).

The rising prevalence of digital refuge among Nigerian adolescents presents significant psychosocial and educational challenges. While digital platforms provide temporary relief, social connection, and distraction from offline stressors, overreliance can hinder the development of adaptive coping strategies, emotional regulation, and interpersonal competence (Balogun et al., 2024; Olatunji, 2024). Adolescents who habitually retreat online in response to loneliness or emotional dependency risk social withdrawal, diminished academic performance, and delayed psychosocial maturation (Awopetu; Shensa et al., 2024; Onukwuli et al., 2023). Digital refuge is particularly salient in contexts where adolescents encounter academic pressures, peer rejection, familial instability, and socio-economic challenges because digital spaces provide immediate access to distraction, emotional validation, social connection, and identity exploration. When offline environments are perceived as stressful, rejecting, or unstable, adolescents may turn to online platforms as alternative environments where they can regulate negative emotions, experience a sense of belonging, and exert greater control over self-presentation.

Online platforms provide immediacy, interactive feedback, and the perception of social support, temporarily alleviating loneliness and psychological distress while reinforcing dependency patterns (Latikka et al., 2024; Yao et al., 2025). Adolescents often curate idealised self-presentations, engage with entertaining or inspirational content, and participate in socially rewarding interactions, creating a cycle of avoidance that undermines the development of

adaptive coping strategies (Moral & Prieto, 2022; Olave et al., 2021). Overreliance on digital refuge may impede face-to-face social competence, resilience, and emotional regulation, paradoxically exacerbating the feelings of isolation and inadequacy that drive such behaviours (Onuoha et al., 2024; Okpe & Jibrin, 2024). This study is particularly timely and relevant because adolescents today navigate unprecedented academic pressures, widespread social media exposure, and evolving family and community dynamics, which have intensified during periods of socio-economic uncertainty and post-pandemic adjustment. Understanding the factors that predict digital refuge in this context can inform targeted interventions to support healthy coping, social connectedness, and psychological well-being among adolescents.

Loneliness, defined as the perception of social disconnection or emotional unfulfilment even in the presence of others, is a key antecedent of digital refuge (Ajibade & Mwalillanda, 2024). Adolescents experiencing chronic loneliness frequently engage in compensatory digital behaviours, including excessive social media use, online gaming, or messaging, as a means of filling emotional voids (Awopetu et al., 2024; Onukwuli et al., 2023). While online interactions may provide temporary relief, they often lack depth, empathy, and authenticity, limiting opportunities for meaningful social connection and reinforcing reliance on digital spaces (Nowland, et al., 2018; Onukwuli et al., 2023). Emotional dependency further amplifies this pattern, as adolescents who rely on digital platforms for affirmation, acceptance, and validation are at risk of developing compulsive engagement habits that interfere with offline responsibilities and relationships (Omokhabi, 2023; Singha & Singha, 2024). Socio-economic instability, family disintegration, and rapid urbanisation often expose adolescents to emotional neglect or limited offline support, prompting them to seek refuge in digital communities (Imbur, 2024; Okonkwo & Nwachukwu, 2023; Akanle et al., 2021). In these “virtual communal compounds,” adolescents experience a sense of visibility, control, and emotional safety often absent in offline environments. However, overreliance on digital refuge may displace opportunities for authentic face-to-face interaction, contributing to social withdrawal, academic disengagement, and reinforcement of loneliness (Fankomo et al., 2025; Balogun et al., 2024).

Social media addiction intensifies the risks associated with digital refuge by fostering patterns of compulsive use, anxiety when offline, and persistent engagement despite negative consequences. It has been linked to academic neglect, withdrawal from family and peer interactions, and increased susceptibility to anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem (Awopetu et al., 2024; Fresku et al., 2025; Maduka, 2025). Algorithm-driven content, reward loops, and

social comparison further reinforce adolescents' reliance on digital spaces, creating a cycle in which digital refuge serves both as a coping mechanism and a source of psychological vulnerability (Maduka, 2025). Despite growing recognition of digital refuge and social media addiction as pressing adolescent mental health concerns, empirical research in sub-Saharan Africa remains limited. Most existing studies have focused on general screen time or problematic internet use without adequately exploring the psychological motivations underpinning digital refuge, particularly the roles of loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction (Awopetu et al., 2024; Fankomo et al., 2025; Maduka, 2025).

Understanding these psychosocial determinants is critical for developing interventions that encourage healthier digital engagement and support adolescents' emotional and social development in the digital age. Moreover, current literature largely overlooks the interplay of psychosocial factors driving digital refuge in the Nigerian context. Without a comprehensive understanding of these determinants, evidence-based interventions remain constrained. Despite growing recognition of digital refuge and social media addiction as critical adolescent mental health concerns, empirical research in sub-Saharan Africa remains limited. Most studies have examined general screen time or problematic internet use without adequately investigating the psychological motivations underlying digital refuge, particularly the roles of loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction (Awopetu et al., 2024; Maduka, 2025). This study, therefore, examines the combined and independent effects of loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction on digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria, with the aim of informing strategies that promote mental health, psychosocial resilience, and responsible digital engagement.

Theoretical Underpinning

This study is grounded in Compensatory Internet Use Theory (CIUT), proposed by Kardefelt-Winther (2014), which provides a psychological framework for understanding why adolescents turn to digital platforms to cope with emotional difficulties. CIUT posits that internet use serves a compensatory function, whereby individuals engage with digital environments not solely for entertainment, but to manage negative emotions, alleviate psychological distress, or escape real-life stressors (Awopetu et al., 2024; Kardefelt-Winther, 2014). The theory shifts focus from the frequency or duration of online activity to the underlying psychological motivations driving engagement, emphasising the emotional drivers of behaviours such as digital refuge (Melodia et al., 2022).

According to CIUT, adolescents experiencing loneliness, low self-esteem, social rejection, or emotional neglect may turn to online spaces for temporary relief, distraction, or social connection (Ajibade & Mwalillanda, 2024). Digital platforms provide a sense of control, anonymity, and immediacy often absent in offline environments, making them particularly attractive for adolescents navigating developmental challenges such as heightened emotional sensitivity and peer dependence (Aruoture & Adegoke, 2024). Activities such as social media browsing, messaging, or online gaming are, therefore, not merely leisure pursuits, but intentional strategies to compensate for real-world deficits, including loneliness and emotional deprivation.

A distinctive feature of CIUT is its focus on psychological causality. Rather than conceptualising excessive internet use as inherently pathological, the theory suggests that such behaviour initially functions as an adaptive coping strategy. Over time, however, repeated reliance on digital spaces may foster emotional dependency and reinforce avoidance of real-life stressors (Moral & Prieto, 2022; Olave et al., 2021). In the Nigerian context, socio-economic instability, family dynamics, and limited access to mental health support may exacerbate adolescents' vulnerability to seeking digital refuge (Okonkwo & Nwachukwu, 2023; Akanle et al., 2021). By framing digital refuge within CIUT, the study highlights how adolescents in Ibadan use online spaces as a compensatory mechanism to manage emotional vulnerabilities such as loneliness and social media addiction. The theory provides a lens for interpreting the findings, showing that adolescents' engagement with digital environments is a purposeful response to psychosocial needs rather than mere recreational activity, thereby connecting emotional experiences, behavioural patterns, and online coping strategies.

Goal of the Study

The study aims to examine the combined and independent effects of loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction on digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria. The present study seeks to fill this gap by investigating the joint and independent effects of loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction on digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan, Nigeria. Specifically, the study aims to:

1. examine the joint and independent predictive effects of loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction on digital refuge.
2. determine gender differences in digital refuge, hypothesising that female adolescents will report higher engagement in digital refuge than male adolescents.

- investigate the predictive role of socio-demographic variables (age and family type) on digital refuge.

By integrating Compensatory Internet Use Theory into the conceptual framework, this study positions digital refuge as a motivated, emotionally adaptive behaviour that may, over time, become maladaptive if reliance on digital platforms substitutes for real-world coping strategies. Findings from this study are expected to inform evidence-based interventions and strategies aimed at promoting healthy digital engagement, psychosocial resilience, and emotional regulation among adolescents, particularly in contexts characterised by socio-economic challenges and limited access to mental health resources.

Methods

Design

This study employed a cross-sectional research design, which is suitable for collecting data at a single point in time from the target population. This design allows for the examination of relationships between the independent variables, loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction, and the dependent variable, digital refuge. By capturing these associations in a single survey, the study provides insights into the psychological factors that influence adolescents' online behaviour within a specific socio-cultural context, without requiring experimental manipulation or longitudinal tracking. The cross-sectional approach is particularly effective for exploring patterns of digital engagement and coping mechanisms among adolescents in a non-clinical, school-based setting (Iannattone et al., 2024).

Study Setting

The study was conducted in Ibadan, the capital city of Oyo State in southwestern Nigeria. Ibadan is a large metropolitan area with a population exceeding 3 million, making it one of the most populous cities in West Africa. The city is characterised by its cultural diversity, a wide range of educational institutions, and a mixture of urban and suburban communities. For this study, selected public and private secondary schools in Ibadan East Local Government were targeted to ensure a representative sample of in-school adolescents from varying socio-economic backgrounds. Ibadan provides an appropriate setting for this research due to its accessibility, high population density, and the increasing prevalence of social media use among its youth, which directly aligns with the study's objectives on digital refuge and psychological correlates.

Sample and Data Collection Procedure

A purposive sampling technique was employed to recruit 415 in-school adolescents in this study. This method was appropriate because it allowed for the systematic inclusion of students who met clearly defined eligibility criteria, thereby reducing selection bias. Participants were drawn from four secondary schools in, Ibadan East Local Government, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, comprising two public and two private institutions. The schools were purposively selected to ensure diversity in student socioeconomic backgrounds, school type, and experiences with social media. Within each school, students from Senior Secondary School classes (SSS1 to SSS3) were targeted, as they were considered to have the cognitive maturity necessary to understand and respond meaningfully to the research questionnaire. Both male and female students were included, and eligibility was restricted to those with access to or prior experience with social media platforms, given the study's focus on digital refuge. The minimum required sample size was determined a priori using Slovin's formula ($n = N / [1 + Ne^2]$), where N represented the total student population in Ibadan East Local Government Area (12,650; Oyo State Ministry of Education, Science and Technology) and e represented a margin of error of 0.05. The calculated minimum sample size was 392 students. To account for potential non-response and incomplete questionnaires, an additional number of participants were recruited, yielding a final sample of 415 students.

Recruitment was conducted during school hours with support from school administrators and class teachers, who assisted in identifying students who met the inclusion criteria. Detailed information about the study, including its objectives, voluntary nature, and confidentiality, was provided to all potential participants. Written informed consent was obtained from students aged 18 years and above, while parental or guardian consent, alongside participant assent, was obtained for students under 18. Two trained research assistants facilitated data collection by administering the questionnaires, clarifying items when necessary, without influencing responses, and ensuring consistency of procedure across the four schools. Strict ethical guidelines were observed: participation was voluntary, students were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without consequence, and confidentiality and anonymity were maintained through the use of coded questionnaires and secure, password-protected data storage accessible only to the research team. Inclusion criteria required that participants (a) be aged 13–19 years, (b) be enrolled in Senior Secondary School (SSS1–SSS3), (c) have access to or experience with

social media platforms, (d) provide informed consent (with parental consent where applicable), and (e) be willing to participate in the study. The final sample represented a diverse and comprehensive group, suitable for examining the relationships among the variables in the study. Data were collected over two months, from October to November 2025, using structured, self-administered questionnaires. Eligible participants completed the questionnaires individually in quiet, designated areas within their schools. Questionnaires were administered in English, and trained research assistants were available to clarify items, when necessary, particularly for participants with limited literacy, without influencing responses. Research assistants remained present throughout the process to ensure adherence to study procedures and maintain a supportive, non-coercive environment. All completed questionnaires were retrieved immediately upon completion and securely stored before analysis. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the data collection process.

Research Instruments

Socio-Demographic Information This section gathered background information from participants, including age, gender, class level, school type (public or private), and frequency of social media use. These variables were used to describe the sample and examine potential influences on digital refuge.

Digital Refuge Scale (DRS)

The Digital Refuge Scale (DRS) was developed by the researcher to assess adolescents' tendency to use digital spaces, particularly social media, as a means of coping with loneliness or emotional stress. Items were generated based on theoretical definitions, prior literature, and systematic observations of adolescent digital behaviours. To ensure content and face validity, the scale underwent thorough expert review, with interrater agreement achieved among three independent specialists in adolescent psychology and digital behaviour. A pilot study involving 54 adolescents tested the scale's psychometric properties, leading to the refinement of the initial 20-item pool to a 14-item instrument by removing items that did not meet the minimum item-total correlation threshold of 0.30. Each item is rated on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Never) to 5 (Always), with higher scores indicating greater reliance on digital spaces as a form of emotional or social refuge. The pilot study demonstrated good internal consistency ($\alpha = .828$), while the main study ($n = 415$) showed excellent reliability ($\alpha = .927$), confirming

the DRS as a psychometrically sound and reliable measure of adolescents' use of digital platforms for emotional regulation and social connection.

Loneliness Scale

The UCLA Loneliness Scale (Version 3; Russell, 1996) was used to assess subjective feelings of loneliness. The 20-item instrument measures perceptions of social relationships and feelings of isolation or lack of companionship. Items are rated on a 4-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (Never) to 4 (Often), with higher scores indicating greater loneliness. The scale has demonstrated excellent psychometric properties across diverse populations, including adolescents, with Cronbach's alpha values between 0.89 and 0.94. In this study, the scale showed strong internal consistency ($\alpha = .844$).

Emotional Dependency Scale

The Emotional Dependency Questionnaire (EDQ; Lemos & Londoño, 2006) was used to measure adolescents' levels of emotional dependency. The 12-item scale assesses reliance on others for approval, comfort, stability, and self-worth, with responses rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree). Higher scores reflect greater emotional dependency. The EDQ has demonstrated strong reliability and validity, including positive correlations with attachment anxiety and low self-esteem. In the present study, the scale showed high internal consistency ($\alpha = .887$).

Social Media Addiction Scale

The Bergen Social Media Addiction Scale (BSMAS; Andreassen et al., 2016) was employed to assess adolescents' addictive tendencies toward social media use. The 6-item instrument, adapted from the Bergen Facebook Addiction Scale, captures six core addiction components: salience, mood modification, tolerance, withdrawal, conflict, and relapse. Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Very Rarely to 5 = Very Often), with higher scores indicating greater addictive tendencies. The BSMAS has strong psychometric properties and is suitable for adolescents, capturing behavioural and psychological aspects that may interfere with academic, social, and developmental functioning. In this study, the scale demonstrated acceptable reliability ($\alpha = .793$).

Data Analysis

Data were analysed using IBM SPSS (version 27). Descriptive statistics, such as means, standard deviations, and frequency counts, were computed to summarise participants' demographic characteristics (age, gender, and parental occupation) and key study variables (loneliness, emotional dependency, social media addiction, and digital refuge). Pearson's correlation coefficients were used to examine bivariate relationships among the psychosocial variables, providing insight into the associations between loneliness, emotional dependency, social media addiction, and adolescents' tendency to seek digital refuge.

Hierarchical multiple regression analysis was conducted to test the first hypothesis, which proposed that loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction would independently and jointly predict digital refuge among adolescents. Loneliness was entered in the first model, followed by emotional dependency in the second, and social media addiction in the third, allowing assessment of each predictor's incremental contribution. Standardised beta coefficients (β), t-values, R, R^2 , and ΔR^2 were reported. The second hypothesis, that female adolescents would score higher on digital refuge than males, was tested using an independent samples t-test. Previous research suggests that female adolescents may be more likely to seek social support and emotional coping through online platforms, making gender a relevant factor (Awopetu et al., 2024; Onuoha et al., 2024). Assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance were checked and satisfied.

The third hypothesis, examining the influence of parental occupation on digital refuge, was tested using one-way ANOVA. Studies indicate that adolescents from different socioeconomic backgrounds may vary in access to digital devices and patterns of online coping, which justifies examining occupation as a predictor (Fankomo et al., 2025). The fourth hypothesis, testing the effect of parental marital status on digital refuge, was also examined using one-way ANOVA. Prior literature highlights that adolescents from single-parent or disrupted households may experience higher emotional stress and rely more on digital spaces for comfort, supporting the inclusion of marital status as a factor (Maduka, 2025). Parametric assumptions were assessed and satisfied for all analyses.

All analyses were interpreted at a 95% confidence interval, with statistical significance set at $p < .05$. This analytical approach provided a framework for understanding the psychosocial determinants of digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan, highlighting the unique and joint contributions of loneliness, emotional dependency, social media addiction, gender, parental

occupation, and parental marital status to adolescents' use of digital platforms for emotional and social coping.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Variable	Category	n	%	M	SD
Gender	Male	192	46.4		
	Female	222	53.6		
Age (years)	10–19	389	93.7	14.89	1.46
Ethnicity	Yoruba	330	79.9		
	Igbo	40	9.7		
	Hausa	17	4.1		
	Others	26	6.3		
Religion	Christian	229	55.7		
	Islam	166	40.4		
	Traditional	16	3.9		
Parental Occupation	Government Worker	109	27.4		
	Private Worker	149	37.4		
	Trader	135	33.9		
	Artisan	5	1.3		
Parental Marital Status	Single Parent	77	19.1		
	Married	292	72.5		
	Separated	14	3.5		
	Divorced	11	2.7		
	Widowed	9	2.2		
Present Class	SS1	45	11.0		
	SS2	135	33.0		
	SS3	228	55.7		
Who Are You Living With	Both Parents	309	75.2		
	Mother Alone	69	16.8		
	Father Alone	11	2.7		
	Relatives	21	5.1		

Note. *M* = Mean; *SD* = Standard Deviation. *Gender coded as: 1 = Male, 2 = Female. SSS means Senior Secondary School*

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the 415 participants involved in the study. The findings show that the sample comprised 192 males (46.4%) and 222 females (53.6%),

indicating a slightly higher proportion of female participants. The age range of respondents was between 10 and 19 years, with a mean age of 14.89 years ($SD = 1.46$), suggesting that the majority of the participants were in their mid-adolescent stage. In terms of ethnic composition, the data reveal that the majority of participants were Yoruba (79.9%), followed by Igbo (9.7%), Hausa (4.1%), and others (6.3%). This distribution reflects the dominant ethnic representation within the study area, which is primarily located in a Yoruba-speaking region. About religion, most respondents identified as Christians (55.7%), followed by Muslims (40.4%), and a small proportion who practised traditional religion (3.9%). This demonstrates that the participants predominantly adhered to one of the two major religions in Nigeria. The findings also show a diverse range of parental occupations, with private sector workers (37.4%) forming the largest group, followed by traders (33.9%), government workers (27.4%), and a small number of artisans (1.3%). This suggests that most of the participants came from households engaged in either formal or informal employment sectors.

In terms of parental marital status, the majority of respondents reported that their parents were married (72.5%), while 19.1% were from single-parent homes. A smaller percentage reported that their parents were separated (3.5%), divorced (2.7%), or widowed (2.2%). This indicates that most participants were raised in two-parent family structures. Regarding educational level, most students were in Senior Secondary 3 (SS3) (55.7%), followed by Senior Secondary 2 (SS2) (33.0%), and Senior Secondary 1 (SS1) (11.0%), suggesting that a significant proportion of the respondents were preparing for final examinations. The data show that the majority of participants (75.2%) lived with both parents, while 16.8% lived with their mother alone, 2.7% with their father alone, and 5.1% with relatives. This pattern indicates that most adolescents in the study were raised in stable two-parent households, which may influence their social and emotional development.

Table 2: Zero-order correlation summary table showing the relationship among Loneliness, Emotional Dependency, Social Media Addiction, and Digital Refuge

Variable	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. Gender	1.54	0.50	—					
2. Age	15.21	6.10	-.06	—				
3. Loneliness	58.47	13.30	-.09	.05	—			
4. Emotional Dependency	32.23	10.81	.09	-.02	.38**	—		
5. Social Media Addiction	15.22	5.71	-.06	-.03	.22**	.45**	—	
6. Digital Refuge	45.24	14.00	-.00	.02	.40**	.33**	.30**	—

Note. ** Significant at 0.01; * Significant at 0.05 Gender coding: 1 = Male, 2 = Female

Table 2 presents results on the relationship between loneliness, emotional dependency, social media addiction, and digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan. Results revealed a significant positive relationship between loneliness and digital refuge ($r = .40, p < .01$), indicating that adolescents who experience higher levels of loneliness are more likely to seek refuge in digital spaces. Similarly, emotional dependency was positively and significantly related to digital refuge ($r = .33, p < .01$), suggesting that adolescents with higher emotional reliance on others tend to use digital environments for comfort and support. Additionally, social media addiction showed a significant positive relationship with digital refuge ($r = .30, p < .01$), implying that excessive engagement with social media is associated with increased use of digital platforms as a refuge. In contrast, gender ($r = -.00, p > .05$) and age ($r = .02, p > .05$) were not significantly related to digital refuge, suggesting that these demographic factors do not influence the tendency to seek digital refuge among the participants.

Table 3: Summary of Hierarchical Multiple Regression Showing the Independent and Joint Influence of Loneliness, Emotional Dependency, and Social Media Addiction on Digital Refuge among Adolescents in Ibadan

Model	Predictor	B	SEB	β	t	p	R	R ²	ΔR^2	F	P
							.40	.16	.16	50.77	<.001
1	Loneliness	0.43	0.06	0.40	7.13	<.001					
2	Loneliness	0.36	0.06	0.34	5.62	<.001					
							.42	.18	.02	29.41	<.001
	Emotional Dependency	0.21	0.08	0.16	2.63	<.01					
							.45	.20	.02	22.21	<.001
3	Loneliness	0.34	0.06	0.32	5.38	<.001					
	Emotional Dependency	0.14	0.08	0.11	1.71	>.05					
	Social Media Addiction	0.38	0.15	0.15	2.57	<.05					

Note. ΔR^2 = change in R^2 from previous

Table 3 presents the results of a hierarchical multiple regression analysis examining the independent and joint influence of loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction on digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan.

In Model 1, loneliness was included as the sole predictor. The model significantly predicted digital refuge ($F(1,271) = 50.77$, $R = .40$, $R^2 = .16$, $p < .001$), indicating that loneliness alone explained 15.8% of the variance in digital refuge. Loneliness was a significant independent predictor ($\beta = 0.397$, $t = 7.13$, $p < .001$), suggesting that adolescents who experience higher levels of loneliness are more likely to use digital spaces as a refuge.

In Model 2, emotional dependency was added to the previous predictor. This model also significantly predicted digital refuge ($F(2,270) = 29.41$, $R = .42$, $R^2 = .18$, $p < .001$), accounting for 17.9% of the variance. The inclusion of emotional dependency resulted in an R^2 change of 0.021, indicating that it contributed an additional 2.1% of variance beyond loneliness. Independently, loneliness ($\beta = 0.336$, $t = 5.62$, $p < .001$) and emotional dependency ($\beta = 0.158$, $t = 2.63$, $p < .01$) were significant predictors. This suggests that adolescents with higher emotional dependency are also more likely to seek digital refuge.

In Model 3, social media addiction was added to the previous predictors. The model remained significant ($F(3,269) = 22.21$, $R = .45$, $R^2 = .20$, $p < .001$), explaining 19.9% of the variance in

digital refuge. The inclusion of social media addiction resulted in an R^2 change of 0.020, showing that it accounted for an additional 2.0% of variance. Independently, loneliness ($\beta = 0.320, t = 5.38, p < .001$) and social media addiction ($\beta = 0.152, t = 2.57, p < .05$) were significant predictors, while emotional dependency ($\beta = 0.107, t = 1.71, p > .05$) was not. This indicates that adolescents who experience higher loneliness and engage more in social media are more likely to use digital spaces as a refuge, whereas emotional dependency has a weaker predictive effect when considered alongside the other variables. Based on these results, the hypothesis is partly supported.

Table 4: Summary of Independent t-test Showing the Influence of Gender on Digital Refuge

Gender	N	\bar{x}	SD	df	t	p
Male	177	45.23	14.12	381	0.07	> .05
Female	206	45.14	13.86			

Table 4 presents result on gender differences in digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan. The results revealed that there is no significant gender difference in digital refuge, $t(381) = 0.07, p > .05$. This indicates that both male ($\bar{x} = 45.23, SD = 14.12$) and female ($\bar{x} = 45.14, SD = 13.86$) adolescents exhibit similar tendencies in seeking refuge in digital spaces. The mean difference suggests that gender does not significantly influence the extent to which adolescents rely on digital environments for emotional or social support. Therefore, the stated hypothesis was rejected.

Table 5: One-Way ANOVA Showing the Influence of Parental Occupation on Digital Refuge Among Adolescents

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1096.799	3	365.600	1.898	> .05
Within Groups	70122.321	364	192.644		
Total	71219.120	367			

Table 5 presents the results of a one-way ANOVA conducted to examine the influence of parental occupation on digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan. The analysis revealed that there was no significant main effect of parental occupation on digital refuge, $(F(3, 364) = 1.898, p > .05)$. This suggests that adolescents' reliance on digital spaces for emotional or psychological comfort does not significantly differ based on parental occupation. Therefore,

the hypothesis stating that parental marital status would significantly influence digital refuge among adolescents was not supported

Table 6: One-Way ANOVA Showing the Influence of Parental Marital Status on Digital Refuge Among Adolescents

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	696.823	4	174.206	0.905	> .05
Within Groups	70999.316	369	192.410		
Total	71696.139	373			

Table 6 presents the results of a one-way ANOVA conducted to determine whether parental marital status significantly influences digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan. The analysis revealed no significant main effect of parental marital status on digital refuge, $F(4, 369) = 0.905, p > .05$. This indicates that adolescents' tendency to seek emotional support and comfort in digital spaces does not significantly vary across parental marital status groups, single, married, separated, divorced, or widowed. Therefore, the hypothesis stated was not supported

Discussion

The study investigated the role of psychosocial factors, specifically loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction, in predicting adolescents' engagement in digital refuge in Ibadan. Through a cross-sectional design, the study examined how these factors influence adolescents' tendency to use digital spaces for emotional and psychological support. A total of four hundred and fifteen adolescents participated in the study. The sample included both male and female adolescents from diverse family backgrounds, with varying parental occupations and marital statuses. The first hypothesis proposed that loneliness, emotional dependency, and social media addiction would independently and jointly predict digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan. The results partly supported this hypothesis. Loneliness consistently emerged as a significant predictor across all models, suggesting that adolescents who experience deficiencies in meaningful social connections are more likely to turn to digital spaces as a compensatory mechanism (Nowland, Necka, & Cacioppo, 2018; Weiss, 1973; Lim et al., 2020; Owodunni, 2022). This aligns with the understanding that online interactions often provide immediate, though sometimes superficial, emotional support, which may not fully meet adolescents' deeper relational needs (Yufan, 2024; Ìme et al., 2024; Wang & Zeng, 2024).

Emotional dependency was significant only in the second model but lost predictive power after the inclusion of social media addiction, indicating that its effect overlaps with broader emotional vulnerabilities and online engagement patterns (Ismael & Naji, 2023; Yao et al., 2025; Gonçalves, Nardi, & King, 2023). Social media addiction emerged as a strong predictor in the final model, reflecting the direct role of compulsive digital engagement in fostering reliance on online environments for coping and emotional regulation (Andreassen et al., 2017; Banyai et al., 2017; Caplan, 2010; Latikka et al., 2024). Socioeconomic pressures may further intensify this pattern, as adolescents under stress use social media to escape daily hardships and seek social inclusion (Badejo & Oriade, 2024; Dasuki & Effah, 2022; Aldamen, 2025). Even among more advantaged youth, digital platforms can substitute for real-world engagement, reinforcing habitual reliance (Anikeze & Okpalaibekwe, 2024). While some studies report no association between loneliness and social media addiction (Obodo & Onwuekwem, 2024), the overall pattern supports the conclusion that loneliness and social media addiction are key psychosocial drivers of digital refuge, whereas emotional dependency plays a weaker role when considered alongside habitual online behaviours. These findings highlight the need for interventions that address emotional isolation and problematic social media use among adolescents in urban Nigerian contexts.

The second hypothesis posited that female adolescents would significantly score higher on digital refuge than their male counterparts. The results of the independent samples t-test indicated no significant gender difference in digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan. Both male and female adolescents demonstrated similar tendencies in seeking refuge in digital spaces, suggesting that gender does not play a decisive role in influencing the extent to which adolescents use digital platforms for emotional or social coping. Consequently, the hypothesis was rejected. The lack of significant gender difference in digital refuge aligns with emerging perspectives emphasising that digital engagement and reliance on social media as a coping mechanism may transcend traditional gender distinctions, particularly in adolescent populations. While previous studies have documented gendered patterns of online behaviour, where females are often observed to engage more deeply with emotion-focused coping and males may lean toward performance-based digital activities such as gaming or fitness tracking (Chen, et al., 2025; Olave et al., 2021), these distinctions may be less pronounced among adolescents in contemporary digital contexts. Socialisation processes, cultural shifts, and the ubiquitous nature of digital technologies might contribute to similar usage patterns among boys and girls, as reflected in the current findings.

Demographic factors such as age, socioeconomic status, and cultural context may exert stronger influence than gender in shaping digital refuge. Adolescents, due to ongoing emotional development and heightened vulnerability to stress, are particularly inclined to seek online spaces for emotional regulation and social connection (Ajayi, et al., 2024; Latikka et al., 2024). In low-resource settings, including parts of Nigeria, digital platforms may provide critical psychological buffers against stressors, irrespective of gender. Badejo and Oriade (2024) highlighted that adolescents facing economic stress often turn to social media as a coping mechanism, suggesting that the need for digital refuge may be driven more by situational and emotional demands than by gendered tendencies. Socio-cultural contexts further shape the adaptive use of digital spaces. Studies on displaced populations and marginalised communities demonstrate that social media serves as a critical tool for maintaining connections, accessing information, and managing stress in environments of social disruption (Aldamen, 2023, 2025; Dasuki & Effah, 2022). While these studies focus on crisis contexts, the underlying principle, that digital refuge is a broadly accessible strategy to manage emotional and social needs, may explain the lack of gender differences observed in the present study.

The third hypothesis posited that adolescents whose parents are government workers would significantly score higher on digital refuge than adolescents whose parents are private workers, traders, or artisans. The results revealed no significant effect of parental occupation on adolescents' use of digital spaces for emotional or psychological comfort. This implies that parental occupation, as an indicator of professional or economic status, does not appear to influence the extent to which adolescents seek refuge in digital platforms. Adolescents, regardless of their parents' work type, seem equally likely to engage with digital environments for emotional regulation, social connection, or stress relief. These findings align with research suggesting that digital refuge may be influenced more strongly by individual, situational, and broader demographic factors than by parental occupation alone. For instance, adolescents' age, emotional development, and psychosocial needs often play a pivotal role in determining reliance on digital spaces for coping (Ajayi, et al., 2024; Latikka et al., 2024). Socioeconomic status (SES), while generally influential in shaping access to technology and patterns of digital engagement, may not align neatly with parental occupation categories in this context. Studies have shown that adolescents facing economic or emotional stress may use social media as a coping mechanism regardless of family income or parental profession (Badejo & Oriade, 2024). Similarly, the cultural and geographic environment, including the availability of technology and social norms around digital use, can create conditions where adolescents'

digital refuge behaviors are largely independent of parental work type (Aldamen, 2023, 2025; Dasuki & Effah, 2022). In essence, the findings suggest that the use of digital platforms as a form of emotional or psychological support among adolescents in Ibadan is a widespread phenomenon that transcends parental occupation.

The fourth hypothesis proposed that adolescents from married parental homes would significantly score higher on digital refuge compared to their peers from single-parent, separated, divorced, or widowed households. The results indicated no significant effect of parental marital status on adolescents' use of digital spaces for emotional or psychological support. This suggests that adolescents' engagement in digital refuge is not determined by whether their parents are married or come from other family structures. Adolescents from all types of households appear equally likely to rely on digital platforms for coping, social interaction, or emotional regulation. Consequently, the hypothesis was not supported. These finding challenges assumptions that family structure directly shapes adolescents' reliance on digital spaces for emotional refuge. While parental support, stability, and household dynamics can influence adolescent well-being, the results imply that digital refuge may function as an independent coping mechanism accessible to adolescents regardless of their family background. The universality of digital engagement among adolescents is consistent with research emphasizing the role of age, emotional development, and psychosocial needs in driving online coping behaviors (Ajayi, et al., 2024; Latikka et al., 2024). Furthermore, the pervasive availability and cultural normalization of digital platforms in contemporary adolescent life may reduce the moderating influence of parental marital status. Social media and online spaces provide consistent access to emotional support, information, and social connectivity, which adolescents may seek irrespective of family structure. Similar findings from studies in other contexts suggest that adolescents' engagement with digital platforms as a form of emotional refuge is shaped more by individual circumstances, peer networks, and situational factors than by household composition (Aldamen, 2023, 2025; Dasuki & Effah, 2022).

Implication and Recommendation

The findings of this study have significant theoretical and practical implications for understanding adolescents' engagement in digital refuge within the Nigerian context. The prominent predictive roles of loneliness and social media addiction suggest that digital spaces function as critical emotional and psychological buffers for adolescents, particularly in urban

environments such as Ibadan. From a theoretical perspective, the results underscore the applicability of the Compensatory Model of Resilience (Zimmerman, 2013) and the Stress-Buffering Model of Social Support (Cohen & Wills, 1985) in explaining adolescents' adaptive reliance on digital platforms. Adolescents experiencing emotional isolation or social deficits appear to compensate through online engagement, highlighting the interplay between psychological vulnerabilities and protective coping mechanisms in shaping mental health outcomes. This contributes to the growing body of evidence that psychosocial factors can differentially influence online behaviour and that digital refuge is a nuanced, context-dependent phenomenon.

Practically, the findings suggest that mental health interventions targeting adolescents should incorporate strategies that recognise the dual role of digital spaces as both supportive and potentially addictive environments. The significant effect of social media addiction in predicting digital refuge implies that habitual online engagement can intensify reliance on digital coping mechanisms, potentially leading to maladaptive behaviours if unmonitored. Intervention programs, therefore, should aim to promote balanced and mindful use of technology, while simultaneously strengthening offline social networks to reduce emotional dependence on virtual platforms. Schools, community centers, and healthcare providers can develop structured programs to enhance peer support, facilitate mentorship, and foster social cohesion among adolescents.

The lack of significant influence of gender, parental occupation, and parental marital status further informs policy and programmatic design. These findings indicate that digital refuge is a broadly accessible coping strategy among adolescents, irrespective of familial or sociodemographic distinctions. Consequently, interventions should target all adolescents, rather than focusing on specific gender or family groups. Policymakers and practitioners should prioritise universal strategies that strengthen emotional literacy, social connectedness, and self-regulation skills. Programs promoting resilience, digital well-being, and emotional intelligence can equip adolescents to manage stressors effectively, while ensuring that online engagement remains adaptive rather than detrimental.

Culturally, these results highlight the necessity of contextualising mental health initiatives within Nigerian urban settings. Digital platforms are not merely recreational tools; they are integral to adolescents' social and emotional landscapes. Community-based interventions should therefore integrate technology-focused psychosocial support, providing guidance on healthy digital habits and fostering awareness of potential risks associated with

overdependence on virtual spaces. Furthermore, parents, educators, and mental health practitioners should be sensitised to the evolving role of digital environments in adolescent coping strategies, encouraging supportive monitoring rather than restrictive oversight. The use of a cross-sectional design in a diverse urban setting like Ibadan allows for the efficient examination of associations between psychosocial factors and digital refuge among adolescents, providing a snapshot of behavioural patterns without experimental manipulation. This approach highlights key predictors of digital coping in real-world contexts and informs future longitudinal or intervention studies aimed at reducing maladaptive online behaviours.

Limitations and Future Directions

While this study provides valuable insights into the predictive roles of psychosocial factors and demographic characteristics on digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional design of the study limits the ability to infer causal relationships between loneliness, emotional dependency, social media addiction, and digital refuge. Although significant associations were identified, it is not possible to determine the directionality of these relationships or how they evolve over time. Future research should consider longitudinal designs to capture temporal dynamics and better understand how psychosocial vulnerabilities influence digital refuge across developmental stages.

Second, the study relied on self-reported measures, which are subject to social desirability bias and reporting inaccuracies. Adolescents may underreport or overreport their engagement with digital platforms and psychosocial experiences, potentially affecting the precision of the findings. Incorporating multi-method approaches, such as digital activity tracking, peer or caregiver reports, and observational assessments, could provide more robust and triangulated data in future studies.

Third, the sample was drawn exclusively from adolescents in urban areas of Ibadan, limiting the generalisability of the findings to rural settings or other cultural contexts in Nigeria. Urban adolescents may have greater access to digital platforms, influencing patterns of digital refuge differently from their rural counterparts, where technological infrastructure and social dynamics may vary. Future research should examine diverse geographic and socio-economic settings to enhance the external validity of the findings and explore potential contextual moderators of digital refuge.

Additionally, while the study examined several psychosocial factors and demographic variables, other relevant influences on digital refuge, such as personality traits, family functioning, peer relationships, and exposure to online risks, were not included. Subsequent

research should adopt a more comprehensive approach by integrating these factors to develop a holistic understanding of adolescents' online coping behaviors. Furthermore, exploring moderating and mediating mechanisms, such as resilience, mental health, and perceived social support, could elucidate the pathways through which psychosocial vulnerabilities contribute to digital refuge.

Although the study focused on the Nigerian context, the rapidly evolving digital landscape warrants continuous investigation into how emerging technologies, social media trends, and cultural shifts shape adolescent coping strategies. Future studies should examine the interplay between technological innovation and psychosocial well-being, particularly in low-resource settings, to inform targeted interventions and culturally responsive policies. In sum, addressing these limitations through longitudinal, multi-method, and contextually diverse research designs will strengthen the evidence base and provide nuanced insights into adolescent digital refuge, informing both theory and practice in mental health promotion and digital well-being.

Conclusion

The study found that loneliness and social media addiction significantly predicted digital refuge among adolescents in Ibadan, while emotional dependency did not show a significant independent effect. Demographic variables such as gender, parental occupation, and parental marital status were also not significant predictors. These findings suggest that digital refuge is primarily driven by emotional vulnerability and habitual online engagement rather than demographic factors, underscoring the need for interventions that address loneliness and promote healthy social media use among adolescents.

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